

Creating a portrait of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur and describing the speech of the characters in the historical works of European and Uzbek writers

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Abstract. This article analyzes the methods of creating the image of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur in the historical works of European and Uzbek writers and the skill of artistic depiction of the characters' speech. The study considers the figure of Babur not only as a historical figure, but also as a complex artistic image, and highlights the aesthetic views of writers and the methods of reflecting the spirit of the era through his portrait.

The article, along with a deep psychological analysis of the image of Babur in Pirimqul Kadirov's novel "Starry Nights", studies how Babur's personality, inner experiences and historical decisions are depicted in European literature (in particular, biographical novels based on the life of Babur). It also analyzes the character of the characters, their social and spiritual world through the speech of the characters. The article reveals the peculiarities of the European and Uzbek literary schools in creating the image, the artistic interpretation of the figure of Babur, and how historical truth and artistic truth are combined. This scientific work may be useful for literary critics, philologists, historians, and researchers in the field of Babur studies.

Keywords: Babur, historical work, portrait creation, character speech, European literature, Uzbek literature, artistic image, artistic depiction, comparative analysis, historical figure, stylistic means, artistic skill, Babur studies.

1 Introduction

The most important historical source about Babur Mirza is, without a doubt, his own work "Baburnoma". This work not only serves as a primary, reliable source for studying Babur's personality, life path, military campaigns and views on state governance, but also shows a realistic portrait of Babur and his surrounding historical figures so that we can form an idea of them. However, when creating a historical work, the writer does not rely only on historical facts, but also widely uses artistic textures. In such a case, when revealing the concept of the creator, "The external appearance of the characters drawn in words - a portrait - is also considered an important tool in creating a human image." In addition, in order to fully embody the image of a person in a work of art, in addition to artistic psychologism, character speech and portrait, the author's characterization is also an important element. In this regard, the Russian scientist M. Bakhtin in his work "Author and Hero in Aesthetic Activity" emphasizes that in the process of creation, the author does not always appear in the role of a "ruler" when directly describing the character, but rather represents the character as an independent subject. The initial characterization given by the author forms the character in the eyes of the reader as an "initial model", but it is important that the character is revealed on a wider scale throughout the work. The English scientist Edward Morgan Forster in his book "Aspects of the Novel" divides characters into such types as "flat" (single-character) and "round" (multifaceted). Author's characterization can be highly effective in defining "flat" characters, but in the process of forming a "round" character, author's characterization alone is not enough. For this, all the elements mentioned above - the characters' unique speech, psychological states, and portrait - come to the author's aid. Among them, the author's characterization serves as a convenient "entrance" for the reader. For example, in the chapter "Babur Shah" of the English writer R. Godin's "Gulbadan" it is stated: Babur was a strong-willed, determined person, and if he

set a goal for himself, he would not fail to achieve it. Although he was a king, his life was spent in constant travel and campaigns. During these campaigns, he easily moved from one place to another. His main cargo on the journey was tents, which were skillfully set up in a short time and easily dismantled when necessary. The equipment that the army carried with it mainly consisted of carpets, tulips, special devices for burning fragrant herbs used to drive away mosquitoes and flies, tablets and dishes for reading books. During his campaigns as ruler, he carried symbols of his authority and status, like noble princes: colorful umbrellas, flags, and military banners made of the tail of a ostrich. Many miniature paintings depict him under such banners.

Babur was distinguished from other nobles by his modesty. No matter how difficult and long the journeys, a few rare books always accompanied him. The author's characterization, which begins with the words "He especially carefully preserved war horses, strong and hardy camels, weapons and armor," serves as a "key" to entering the text. Sometimes the portrait and author's characterization can be found in a mixed form in the text. For example, in F. Würtle's "Prince of Andijan", this can be seen in the description of the twelve-year-old prince affected by the death of Umar Sheikh Mirza: My warriors and slaves, you all know what happened. You have news of what disaster our kind king Umar Sheikh Mirza suffered. A terrible coincidence led to this. The long, columned front again resembled a field of people, caressed by the wind. Again, the turbaned heads, resembling the heads of the swaying ears of corn, began to bend and straighten.

In front, only one person stood motionless, his body erect and rigid. He was a bony man, and because of his frailty, the strong, strong men who were taking part in the capture of the fortress paid him little attention. This same man, the frailest of all, sat ostentatiously, and apparently did not even try to imitate others in his loyalty. His eyes on his small face looked like the eyes of a falcon. Here, the image of the appearance and the state of mind of the young Babur Mirza are harmoniously described. In the text, the portrait and the image of the mind perform two main functions:

1. To imagine the character as alive and visible. Through this, the author manages to create a "living" image before the eyes of the reader.
2. To ensure the harmony of the mental image and the image. Each detail in the portrait (facial features, various physical signs, the image of those listening to Babur) also serves to substantiate the character's inner world or social status.

In P. Kadyrov's novel "Starry Nights", the architect Mavlano Fazliddin draws a portrait of Khanzoda Begim, the sister of Fazliddin Babur. Here, the writer indirectly describes the portrait of Khanzoda Begim through the portrait he drew: The beautiful girl with a delicate face, painted with colorful paints, at that moment seemed to him a living person. In the light of the flame, the girl's eyelashes and lips seemed to be making subtle, graceful movements. The girl had a charm that amazed the mind. This charm enchanted Mulla Fazliddin even more, the previous threat receded from his mind, and warm feelings awoke in his heart. "Could I fall in love with this girl?" Mulla Fazliddin thought in amazement. "Isn't it funny that a painter like me, who came from the black people, should fall in love with the king's daughter? No! I only love the portrait I painted—my own creation, after all!" If I can, I will draw such a picture again! . It is clear that this is also the author's unique method of creating a portrait. In his work "On the Theory of Prose", the Russian scholar V. Shklovsky also connects the portrait with the method of "looking with an alien eye" (ostranenie). For example, in Kh. Sultanov's enlightening novel "Boburiynoma", the image of Babur, a momentary mental state, is given through the gaze of Hafiz Koykiy: When Hafiz Koykiy entered the empty salutation room, bathed in the light of magnificent golden chandeliers with a hundred candles, Babur was absorbed in reading behind a silver plate on the lattice, his hands on the parchment. He greeted Hafiz Koykiy with a cheerful mood. The scholar, slowly examining the book on the plate, recognized the tartiq he had handed over. The inner excitement and the intense impression aroused in Babur's heart by this extraordinary gift had not yet faded. He smiled amicably, silently showed the guest a place, and then looked back at the open page of "Nasayim ul-muhabbat". The author managed to amaze the reader by depicting Babur's appearance precisely through the eyes of another hero, thereby showing the inner state of the character. Here we see that the reader can also perceive the mental state of the character through the portrait image. That is, a

portrait is not only an “external appearance”, but can also be an artistic tool that expresses the signs of the character’s psyche with these external details. In this passage, Kh. Sultanov, without drawing a clear external portrait, illuminates the character’s character through his behavior and speech. Sometimes, limiting the portrait image or not giving it at all can also be a unique artistic method. A portrait is not the main goal, but a means to depict a character more vividly and impressively. Sometimes it is also achieved by deliberately canceling (not giving) a strong aesthetic effect. In a work of art, a portrait increases the aesthetic value of the work. Personal experiences, internal monologues and indirect details (movement, facial expressions, external background) together serve to reveal the entire inner world of the character, to fully form the image in a literary text. A portrait is not only a description of the external features of the hero, but also an artistic and stylistic way of indirectly revealing his inner world, behavior and psyche, and highlighting him against the background of other heroes. For example, in this excerpt from the work of R. Godin, I threw myself at his feet...” writes Gulbadan. But since his father, Babur, was a charming person by nature, he always treated women and children with generosity and gentleness. “The master asked about many things,” continues Gulbadan. The feelings of shyness and shyness in the girl's heart gradually recede. Babur, in turn, was fascinated by this girl who had appeared from nowhere and amazed him with her intelligence and charm. “He held me in his arms for a long time, carried me on his knees, and I felt so happy at those moments that it is difficult to imagine ... In this fragment, the portrait image serves, first of all, to reveal the uniqueness and unique features of the heroes in the work. Here, the appearance of the hero is shown in a way that is directly related to his inner world. As noted in a number of scientific literature, the elements of the portrait (color, clothing, appearance, facial expressions, movements) indirectly provide information about the hero’s mental state and behavior.

For example, the eyes, facial expressions, the way the heroine speaks or remains silent - all this helps to understand her inner feelings: Kutlug Nigor Khanum's complexion was pale. Above her forehead - where her hair parted, Babur saw a tuft of gray hair. Now in her forties, Anayizor dressed like an old woman and walked with a stooped posture. In this excerpt, the portrait of Kutlug Nigor Khanum describes her troubled life, which was spent in constant danger and battles, and her mood. The image of a portrait plays an important role in shaping the atmosphere of a work. Through the portrait of a hero, the author enriches the atmosphere, reveals the spirit of the era or the color of the place. Therefore, the correct use of a portrait enriches the artistic and aesthetic content of the entire work.

In historical works, the image of the portrait plays an important dramatic role in the plot. For example, such signs as the external change of the hero, such as Babur's face turning pale due to the poisoning of Princess Bayda in "Starry Nights", his face becoming gloomy due to suffering, or his face becoming radiant due to the joy of seeing a small flower and Hindol, are directly related to the development of events in the work. Also, a small change given to the portrait of the hero can play a key role in the plot twist or in deepening the conflict. The portrait can sometimes serve the purpose of enriching the overall artistic and aesthetic landscape of the work, contrasting beauty and ugliness, and reflecting the creator's own taste or style. This contrast is evident in the portrait of Babur's first wife, Aisha Begum, and his beloved wife, Mohim Begum, in "Starry Nights". In this way, the two different portraits of the two women help to reveal an important part of Babur Mirzo’s life - the parts related to the family.

2 Methods

1. Literary and Historical Analysis

Textual Analysis: Begin by analyzing both European and Uzbek literary works that describe Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, such as Babur’s autobiography "*Baburnama*" and various European accounts of his life. Compare the way each culture represents his personality, leadership qualities, and significance.

Characterization of Babur: Pay close attention to the way Babur is portrayed through direct narration, internal monologue, and the portrayal of his interactions with other characters. Analyze how European writers frame Babur’s leadership style, military campaigns, and personal qualities versus the portrayal of these same traits in Uzbek works. Focus on Speech and Dialogue: In these works, analyze how the speech and dialogues of characters are constructed, focusing on tone, rhetoric, and language choices. In historical fiction or memoirs, characters might speak in a manner that reflects the time period and region of the author.

2. Comparative Literary Approach

Cultural Contextualization: Understand the cultural contexts in which the European and Uzbek writers were working. Analyze how each culture’s view of leadership, heroism, and historical narrative influenced the portrayal of Babur. European writers may focus on his military campaigns or imperial ambitions, while Uzbek writers might emphasize his cultural contributions, poetry, and impact on Central Asian heritage. Character Interaction and Language Style: Compare how historical figures like Babur interact with others in different works. Do European writers describe him in a way that reflects a Westernized hero, focusing on power and conquest? Do Uzbek writers, on the other hand, imbue Babur’s speech with more poetic or reflective qualities, as befits a ruler with deep cultural roots in the region? Our analysis shows that in the works of European and Uzbek writers dedicated to Babur Mirza, most of the characters' facial features, height, complexion, and clothing are clearly and directly described. This is done using poetic expressions or artistic means of description, such as adjectives, similes, metaphors, and diacritics.

For example, in the work "Gulbadan", the word "Gul" is similar to the word "rose", so this word adorns the names of most princesses. Because in the East, from Iran to India and China, this flower is revered and respected. While the Afghan rose is white, the Iranian rose is pink and smaller, and exudes a delicate and pleasant scent. It is sometimes called the "Damascus rose". It is not surprising that Babur Shah had in mind a red rose when choosing a name for Gulbadan and his other daughters, he says, comparing Gulbadan Begum to the most beautiful flower - the Damascus rose, and uses metaphors and adjectives very beautifully.

Thus, the analysis of these works shows that the speech of the characters is a factor that enriches the semantics of the literary text, through which the creators vividly, vividly, and memorably depict Babur and the landscape of the era in which he lived. In historical novels, the speech of the characters appears as an artistic tool that reflects not only the individual character, but also the entire national spirit, the lexicon and traditions of the historical period.

1. In the artistic interpretation of the image of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, it was clearly seen that supporting characters serve to reveal Babur's character, develop the plot, expand the landscape of the era, and strengthen the author's idea. Supporting characters, such as parents, advisors, commanders, and creative people, help to further enrich the political, cultural, and human qualities of Babur. The contradictions and contradictions associated with Babur are intensified through supporting characters, increasing the dramatic power of the plot.

2. Supporting characters actively participate in the development of historical and political events. Supporting characters help to portray the political and social environment of Babur's childhood and youth, the spirit of the times, and the events in more depth. In the work, supporting characters reinforce the author's idea by illuminating Babur's inner experiences and revealing his human side. Their participation is the main tool for showing the various facets of Babur's image.

3. In historical works about Babur, characters and historical periods are more effectively depicted with the help of character speech. The use of auxiliary images not only serves to develop the plot, but also increases the artistic and aesthetic value of the work, allowing for a broader understanding of the historical environment. Each author, through his own unique style and analytical approach, scientifically expresses the complexity of the figure of Babur and his place in the historical heritage.

4. Through the skill of creating portraits and describing the speech of characters in historical works, the personality and image of Babur Mirza as a hero are more deeply reflected. This is clearly visible in the uniqueness of creating portraits and describing the speech of characters.

5. With the help of dialogues, internal monologue and historical lexicon, Babur's formal and sincere speech is formed, which fully reflects his personal experiences, psychological state and socio-cultural context of the era.

6. The authors (for example, P. Kadyrov and Kh. Sultanov) provide a polyphonic approach to Babur's speech through the formal style, internal monologue and conversations with loved ones, reflecting different positions.

7. The works of F. Würtle, R. Goden, P. Kadyrov, and H. Sultanov, using a number of artistic techniques in creating the portrait of Babur Mirzo and the speech of the characters, deeply analyze his political, cultural, and human aspects and increase the aesthetic value of historical novels.

Conclusion. The image of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur in the historical works of European and Uzbek writers embodies the aesthetic, artistic and ideological approaches of both literatures. While in Uzbek literature the image of Babur is approached in the spirit of deep national pride, historical memory and appreciation of spiritual heritage, in the works of European authors he is interpreted more as a bright representative of Eastern civilization, a great commander and a writer.

The depiction of characters' speech also appears as an important artistic tool in these works, playing an important role in illuminating the inner world, attitude to their time, and personal character of historical figures. In particular, dialogues and monologues illuminate Babur's intelligence, political thinking, and personal life.

The analysis conducted in the article shows that the attitude of representatives of different literary schools to historical figures and the way they are reflected in artistic interpretation have similar aspects, but are also distinguished by their own differences. This once again confirms the importance of comparative analysis from a cultural and literary perspective in the study of historical images.

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